

УДК 691

MODERN COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENTS

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Annotation: This article describes the characteristics of composite reinforcement. On the basis of the conducted studies, positive and negative properties are given, ways of practical application are indicated.

Keywords: Non-metallic fiber, binder, epoxy, polyester resin, equal-strength replacement, fiberglass, thermal expansion coefficient, alkaline environment of concrete,

Аннотация: В этой статье дается характеристика композитной арматуре. На основании проведенных исследований приводятся положительные и отрицательные свойства, указывается пути практического применения.

Ключевые слова: Неметаллическое волокно, связующее вещество, эпоксидная, полиэфирная смола, равнопрочная замена, стеклопластика, коэффициент температурного расширения, щелочная среда бетона.

Composite reinforcement is building reinforcement based on non-metallic fibers bonded with a composite composition. For the manufacture of fittings, fiberglass, basalt fiber, carbon fiber, etc. are usually used. These fibers can be used alone or in combination. In practice, two types of composite reinforcement are most widely used: based on glass fiber alone and based on basalt fiber alone. This is where such names as "fiberglass rebar" and "basalt rebar" come from. The physical body of composite reinforcement conventionally consists of two parts

- the main trunk, which sets the main strength characteristics of the reinforcement, which is usually a bundle of parallel fibers connected by a composite binder based on epoxy, polyester resins;
- the outer layer, which is responsible for the properties of adhesion to concrete, as a rule, is a unidirectional winding of fibers in a spiral (reminiscent of steel reinforcement of a periodic profile). To date, such reinforcement has received the greatest distribution precisely abroad, for example, the first mass production of composite reinforcement was launched in the USA already in 1974. The largest number of major global manufacturers of composite rebar is also located in the United States. Composite reinforcement does not corrode, it is resistant to aggressive environments. Refers to the materials of the first group of chemical

resistance, including the alkaline environment of concrete. A layer of corrosion, building up on traditional steel reinforcement, can today increase its diameter by 8 times, which leads to the appearance of cracks and even rupture of the concrete structure.

1. Composite rebar has approximately 2.5-3 times greater tensile strength than steel rebar for the same diameter. For this reason, the concept of "equivalent replacement" has been introduced, in which steel reinforcement is replaced with a composite one with a smaller diameter, but with the same tensile strength.
2. Composite reinforcement is 5 times lighter than steel with equal diameter and 11 times lighter with equal strength diameter. This saves on transportation, reduces the weight of the final concrete structure.
3. Composite reinforcement is much cheaper than steel reinforcement with equal strength replacement.
4. Such reinforcement has a coefficient of thermal expansion, which is almost identical to the coefficient of thermal expansion of concrete.
5. Composite reinforcement has low thermal conductivity and is not a cold bridge. For example, a fiberglass composite has a thermal conductivity of 0.48 W/m•K, while a metal has an average of 56 W/m•K. Thus, fiberglass is 100 times less thermally conductive than metal.
6. Being a dielectric, composite reinforcement (with the exception of carbon fiber) is radio-transparent and magnetically inert.
7. Does not lose strength under the influence of low temperatures. Operating temperature range from -70 °C to +100 °C.

Composite reinforcement is used:

- in foundations below ground level (today, fiberglass reinforcement is the best reinforcing material for strip foundations and pouring of foundation slabs);
 - as flexible connections;
 - for the manufacture of lighting poles, power transmission line supports, insulating traverses of power transmission lines;
 - for road construction: when strengthening the roadbed, bridges, fences;
 - to reinforce such products as: road and paving slabs, fence slabs, curbstones, posts and supports, railway sleepers;
 - in structures operating under conditions of accelerated corrosion of steel reinforcement and concrete (berths, dry docks, reinforcement of the embankment by concreting), as well as in structures subjected to general corrosion and dynamic loads during operation.
- Conclusions The main disadvantages of any composite reinforcement are the following:
- the modulus of elasticity of composite reinforcement is almost 4 times lower than that of steel, even with the same diameter (in other words, it is easily bent). For this reason, it can be used in foundations, road slabs, etc., but the use in ceilings requires additional calculations;
 - when heated to a temperature of 600 °C, the compound that binds the reinforcement fibers softens so much that the reinforcement loses its elasticity

completely. To increase the resistance of the structure to fire in the event of a fire, it is necessary to take additional measures for the thermal protection of structures in which composite reinforcement is used;

- Composite reinforcement, unlike steel, cannot be welded by electric welding. The solution to the problem is the installation of steel tubes at the ends of the reinforcing bars (in the factory), to which it will already be possible to apply electric welding.

References:

1. Mukhtoraliyeva, M. A., Mamadaliyev, A. T., Umarov, I. I., & Sharopov, B. X. Development of technology on the basis of scientific achievements.«. *Матрица научного познания*, 28, 4-12.
2. Ризаев, Б. Ш., Мамадалиев, А. Т., Мухитдинов, М. Б., & Мухторалиева, М. А. (2022). Прочностные и деформативные свойства внецентренно-сжатых железобетонных колонн в условиях сухого жаркого климата. *Научный электронный журнал «матрица научного познания*, 27.
3. Абдуллаев, М. Т., & Мамадалиев, А. Т. (2022). Изучение эффективности дражирования семян хлопчатника в водном растворе минеральных удобрений и композиции микроэлементов.«. *Экономика и социум*, (1), 92.
4. Mamadaliyev, A., Mamadjonov, Z., Arislanov, A., & Isomiddinov, O. (2022). ҚИШЛОҚ ХЎЖАЛИГИДА УРУҒЛИК ЧИГИТЛАРНИ АЗОТ ФОСФОРЛИ ЎҒИТЛАР БИЛАН ҚОБИҚЛАШ. *Science and innovation*, 1(D5), 180-189.
5. Мамадалиев, А. Т. (2021). Теоретическое обоснование параметров чашеобразного дражирующего барабана. *Universum: технические науки*, (6-1 (87)), 75-78.
6. Ризаев, Б. Ш., Мамадалиев, А. Т., Мухитдинов, М. Б., & Одилжанов, А. (2022). Анализ эффективности использования пористых заполнителей для лёгких бетонов. *Экономика и социум*, (2), 93.
7. Sh, B. R., Mamadaliyev, A. T., Mukhitdinov, M. B., & Mukhtoraliyeva, M. A. Study of changes in the strength and deformation properties of concrete in a dry hot climate. *Universum. Технические науки: электрон научн. журн-2022*, 4, 97.
8. Tuxtamirzayevich, M. A. (2020). Study of pubescent seeds moving in a stream of water and mineral fertilizers. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 489-493.
9. Ризаев, Б. Ш., Мамадалиев, А. Т., Фозилов, О. К., & Шаропов, Б. Ў. (2022). ПРОЧНОСТНЫЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ЛЕГКОГО БЕТОНА НА ПОРИСТЫХ ЗАПОЛНИТЕЛЯХ. *Universum: технические науки*, (6-3 (99)), 11-15.
10. Sh, B. (2022). Rizaev, AT Mamadaliyev, MB Mukhitdinov, MA Mukhtoraliyeva Study of changes in the strength and deformation properties of

concrete in a dry hot climate. *Universum. Технические науки: электрон научн. журн*, (4), 97.

11. Tuxtamirzaevich, M. A. (2021). Presowing Treatment of Pubescent Cotton Seeds with a Protective and Nutritious Shell, Consisting of Mineral Fertilizers in an Aqueous Solution and a Composition of Microelements. *Design Engineering*, 7046-7052.

12. Ризаев, Б. Ш., Мамадалиев, А. Т., Мухитдинов, М. Б., & Прочностные, М. М. деформативные свойства внецентренно-сжатых железобетонных колонн в условиях сухого жаркого климата. *Матрица научного познания*, 2-2.

13. Гафуров, К., Росабоев, А., & Мамадалиев, А. (2007). Дражирование опущенных семян хлопчатника с минеральным удобрением. *ФарПИ илмий-техник журнали. – Фаргона*, (3), 55-59.

14. Ризаев, Б. Ш., Мамадалиев, А. Т., Мухитдинов, М. Б., & Одилжанов, А. З. Ў. (2022). ВЛИЯНИЕ АГРЕССИВНЫХ СРЕД НА ДОЛГОВЕЧНОСТЬ ЛЕГКОГО БЕТОНА. *Universum: технические науки*, (2-2 (95)), 47-51.

15. Mamadaliev, A. (2021). Theoretical study of the movement of macro and micro fertilizers in aqueous solution after the seed falls from the spreader. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.

16. Мамадалиев, А. Т., & Мухторалиева, М. А. БХ Шарапов Принципы обучения специальностям в области строительства. *Научный электронный журнал «матрица научного познания»*.

17. Ризаев, Б. Ш., Мамадалиев, А. Т., Мухитдинов, М. Б., & Одилжанов, А. (2022). Анализ эффективности использования пористых заполнителей для лёгких бетонов. *Экономика и социум*, (2), 93.

18. Umarov, I. I., Mukhtoraliev, M. A., & Mamadaliyev, A. T. (2022). Principles of training for specialties in the field of construction. *Jurnal. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. UKRAINA.-2022*.

19. Arislanov, A., Abdullaev, M., Mamadaliev, A., Mamadjonov, Z., & Isomiddinov, O. (2022). ПАХТА ҲОСИЛДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШДА УРУҒЛИК ЧИГИТЛАРНИ МИНЕРАЛ ЎҒИТЛАР БИЛАН ҚОБИҚЛАШ ВА ЭЛЕКТРОКИМЎВИЙ ҲАОЛЛАШГАН СУВ БИЛАН ИВИТИБ ЭКИШ. *Science and innovation*, 1(D5), 171

20. Mamadaliev, A. (2012). ТУКЛИ ЧИГИТЛАРНИ ҚОБИҚЛАШ БАРАБАНИНИНГ ПАРАМЕТРЛАРИНИ НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАШ. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.

21. Mamadaliev, A. (2002). УРУҒЛИК ЧИГИТЛАРНИ МАКРО ВА МИКРОЎҒИТЛАР КОМПОЗИЦИЯЛАРИ БИЛАН ҚОБИҚЛАШ

ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ ВА ҚУРИЛМАЛАРИ. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.

22. Mamadaliev, A. (2019). THEORETICAL SUBSTANTIATION OF PARAMETERS OF THE CUP-SHAPED COATING DRUMS. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.

23. Мамадалиев, А. Т., & Мамаджанов, З. Н. (2022). Минерал ўғитлар ва микроэлементли композицияларни сувдаги эритмаси билан қобиқланган тукли чигитларни лаборатория-дала шароитида синаш натижалари. *Экономика и социум*, (2), 93.

24. Росабоев, А. Т., Мамадалиев, А. Т., & Тухтамирзаев, А. А. У. (2017). Теоретическое обоснование параметров капсулирующего барабана опущенных семян. *Science Time*, (5 (41)), 246-249.

25. Bakhodir, R., Adkhamjon, M., & Bakhtiyorovich, M. M. (2022). SHRINKAGE DEFORMATIONS OF CONCRETE IN NATURAL CONDITIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Universum: технические науки*, (2-7 (95)), 20

26. Shamshidinov, I. T., Mamadaliev, A. T., & Mamajanov, Z. N. (2014). Optimization of the process of decomposition of aluminosilicate of clays with sulfuric acid. In *The First International Conference on Eurasian scientific development* (pp. 270-275).

27. Мамадалиев, А. Т., Мамаджонов, З. Н., & Арисланов, А. С. ҚИШЛОҚ ХЎЖАЛИГИДА УРУҒЛИК ЧИГИТЛАРНИ АЗОТ ФОСФОРЛИ ЎҒИТЛАР БИЛАН ҚОБИҚЛАШ.

28. Ризаев, Б. Ш., Мамадалиев, А. Т., & Умаров, И. И. (2022). Деформации усадки бетона в условиях сухого жаркого климата. *Экономика и социум*, (1)

29. Ризаев, Б. Ш., Мамадалиев, А. Т., Мухитдинов, М. Б., & Одилжанов, А. З. Ў. (2022). ВЛИЯНИЕ АГРЕССИВНЫХ СРЕД НА ДОЛГОВЕЧНОСТЬ ЛЕГКОГО БЕТОНА. *Universum: технические науки*, (2-2 (95)), 47-51.

30. Mamadaliyev, A. T., & Umarov, I. (2022). Texnikaning rivojlanish tarixi. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 2(1), 232-235.

31. Rosaboev, A., & Mamadaliyev, A. (2019). Theoretical substantiation of parameters of the cup-shaped coating drums. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 6(11), 11779-11783.

32. Мамадалиев, А. Т. (2013). Институт механизации и электрификации сельского хозяйства, г. Янгийул, Республика Узбекистан. *Редакционная коллегия*, 174.

33. Bakhodir, R., Adkhamjon, M., & Isroil, U. (2022). Deformativity of reinforced concrete columns from heavy concrete under conditions dry hot climate. *Universum: технические науки*, (1-3 (94)), 59-63.
34. Мамаджанов, З., Мамадалиев, А., Бакиева, Х., & Сайфиддинов, О. (2022). СУЮҚ ЎҒИТАММИАКАТЛАР ОЛИШ ВА УЛАРНИ ИШЛАТИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(A7), 309-315.
35. Bakhodir, R., Adkhamjon, M., Muzaffar, M., & Mukhtasar, M. (2022). STUDY OF CHANGES IN THE STRENGTH AND DEFORMATION PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE IN A DRY HOT CLIMATE. *Universum: технические науки*, (4-12 (97)), 39-43.